

READING HABITS OF INTERMEDIATE PUPILS IN KAPUAL ELEMENTARY SCHOOL, OMAR DISTRICT, MINISTRY OF BASIC, HIGHER AND TECHNICAL EDUCATION, DIVISION-SULU

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to determine the reading habits to academic learning of selected pupils in Kapual Elementary School at Omar District, MBHTE, division-Sulu as perceived by the students in school year 2023-2024. It employed descriptive design with 100 student-respondents taken through subjective sampling method. The following are findings of this study: The student-respondents are mostly between 11-12 years old, female, enrolled in grade VI, and belong to section A. The tables also show that there are significant differences and imbalances among the groups in each category, indicating skewed distributions of age, gender, grade level, and section. The student-respondents have a high positive attitude towards reading habits in most of the categories, except for frequency of reading, where they have a moderate positive attitude. The tables also show that there are some variations among the student-respondents in their agreement with the statements in each category, indicating different levels of reading habits. The student-respondents at Kapual Elementary School, MBHTE, Sulu have different perceptions of their reading habits depending on their age, and grade level. The other demographic variables, such as gender and section, do not affect their perceptions on their reading habits. The result of correlation test reveals that most of the sub-categories are positively correlated with each other, except for frequency of reading, which is negatively correlated with impact to academic learning. However, between frequency of reading and purpose of reading books, and various print sources preferred for reading show no significant correlation. The result also reveals that the strongest correlation is between purpose of reading books and impact to academic learning, while the weakest correlation is between frequency of reading and impact to academic learning.

Keywords: *Reading skills, Reading habits, Intermediate grade,*

INTRODUCTION

When schools were closed during pandemic, the problems on the very high incidence of learning poverty arise. It was due to the shift from face-to-face classes to blended learning which results in poor academic learning and poor reading habits among pupils. In fact, In the Philippines for the year 2019, there were 69.5 percent who were unable to read and increased to 90 percent in 2021. A joint report by UNICEF in partnership with UNESCO and the World Bank showed that learning poverty is being unable to read and understand a simple text by age of 10.

Zahid (2022) pointed out that Reading is a springboard of any literacy programme. It is one of the oldest habits of human civilization, particularly among extraordinary personalities. It is an excellent source of conscious learning and is regarded as the art of interpreting printed and written words. Reading helps in the accuracy of information, attitude, judgement, belief and moral. Many people believe there have been severe decline in reading habits since the invention of the Internet; however, most think that Internet has increased reading habits and not diminished them. In the past, libraries were a great source for fact findings and information acquisition; now, reading culture is declining and people need more time to visit libraries physically. Libraries were known as a place of creative thinking, information and research activities in the past.

Reading is a means of seeking knowledge, information or entertainment through the written words. Reading is said to be a means of language acquisition, communication and sharing information and ideas (Rwanda Book Development Initiative, 2011). Reading is not only the process of interpretation or understanding the text, but an interactive session with the thoughts of the greatest thinkers of the past, present and future genre. It provides an opportunity to transcend into a new journey with own understanding and experience of the subject and promotes new thinking.

(Rattan, 2013), Reading is one of the most important components of our language and it is an essential tool for lifelong learning for all learners. The reading, especially is a resource for continued education, for the acquisition of new knowledge and skills, for gaining information through the media, especially newspapers, books, radio, television, and the computers (Chettri & Rou, 2013). The reading habit is an essential and important aspect for crating the literate society in this world. It shapes the personality of an individual and it helps them to develop the proper thinking methods and creating new ideas (Chauhan & Lal, 2012).

Reading habit is an active skill based process of constructing meaning and gaining knowledge from oral, visual and written text. Reading habits are the intellectual activities for giving more information, knowledge and learn to various types of things and their activities (Babu & Durgaiah, 2016). Reading habits also are increasingly important in the contemporary environment of rapid technological change in the global level (Asokan & Dhanavandan, 2013). Reading is one of the most important skills because it leads to

knowledge, self-improvement, and better comprehension of the world around us. Even though that is common knowledge, many seem to be running out of time for reading,

Due to the perception that there is a fading interest in real reading, meaning, in reading long text that requires comprehension and focus. With the internet revolutionizing our world, there is an impatience for fast information that can be picked up from a meme, an art card, a chat, or a video. Often, even an article that takes five minutes to read is seen as too long. If graduates of past years have retained poor reading skills, what is the situation today? Though a lot has been done in reading/reading habits, there is a need to investigate if, and why, there is a decline in the reading culture of pupils; what these pupils do with their leisure time; their perception about reading; etc. Keeping in view the importance of reading habits.

Therefore, it is against this background that this study was conceived, to specifically; investigate the reading habits amongst pupils of kapual elementary school. This study attempted to know the impact of reading habits on the academic learning of the pupils. The study also sought to establish if there exists a correlation between reading habits and academic learning of the pupils.

Research questions:

This study determined the Reading habits to academic learning of selected pupils in kapual elementary school at Omar District, MBHTE, Division of Sulu as perceived by the students in school year 2023-2024, Specifically, this Research gathered information to answer each of the following questions.

1. What is the Socio- demographic Profile of the respondents in terms of;
 - 1.1 Age;
 - 1.2 Gender;
 - 1.3 Grade level; and
 - 1.4 Section?
2. What is the extent of reading habits of intermediate pupils at Kapual Elementary School, MBHTE, Sulu in terms of;
 - 2.1 Preferred places for reading books;
 - 2.2 Purpose of reading books;
 - 2.3 Frequency of reading; and
 - 2.3 Various print sources preferred for reading?
3. Is there a significant difference in reading habits of intermediate pupils in Kapual Elementary School, MBHTE, Sulu when data are grouped according to
 - 3.1 Age;
 - 3.2 Gender;
 - 3.3 Grade level; and
 - 3.4 Section?
4. Is there a significant correlation among the sub-categories subsumed under the Reading habits to academic learning of pupils in Kapual Elementary School, MBHTE, Sulu?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

Research Design was used in research to refer to the researcher's plan of how to proceed. This design allows data to be collected at a single point in time and can be used for a descriptive study as well as determination of relationship between variable.

A descriptive research design method was employed in this study. Thus, this study intended to describe, quantify, and infer as well as to discover relationships among variables which involves:

1. Demographic profile of Pupils according to Age, Gender, Grade level, Section.
2. Extent of reading habits of the selected pupils at Capual Elementary School, MBHTE, division-Sulu in terms of Preferred places for reading books, Purpose of reading books, Frequency of reading, Various print sources preferred for reading
3. The significant difference in the extent of reading habits to academic learning of pupils in kapual Elementary School, MBHTE, Sulu when grouped according to Age, Sex, Grade level, Section.
4. The significant correlation among the sub-categories subsumed under the Reading habits to academic learning of pupils in kapual Elementary School, MBHTE, Sulu?

The study was conducted among selected pupils at kapual Elementary School, MBHTE, division-Sulu during the fiscal year 2023-2024.

The respondents of this study are the one hundred (100) selected pupils at kapual Elementary School, MBHTE, Sulu, the main source of data which was quantified to answer the research questions in this study. Library and internet was the source of information that will be used to enrich the theoretical and conceptual frameworks of this research, the data from the respondents will be collected through the use of questionnaires.

Research Locale

The study was conducted among intermediate pupils at kapual Elementary School, Ministry of Basic Higher Technical Education (MBHTE), Division of Sulu during the Academic year 2023-2024.

Respondents of The Study

The respondents of the study were One hundred (100) intermediate pupils in Capual Elementary School, Ministry of Basic Higher Technical Education (MBHTE), Sulu Division during the School year 2023-2024.

Thirty (30) selected pupils were drawn to represent each of the grade level. Table below shows the distribution of samples in this study.

Sampling Design

In this study, the researcher used purposive sampling, also known as judgmental selection or subjective sampling is a form of non-probability sampling in which researchers rely on their own judgment when choosing members of the population to participate in their surveys.

The researcher was purposively choose one hundred (100) respondents from Capual Elementary School. The use of purposive sampling study and help the study to meet its goals. Distribution of Target Samples

Capual elementary School, MBHTE, division-Sulu	Number of Respondents
GRADE IV	30
GRADE V	30
GRADE VI	40
TOTAL	100

Data Gathering Procedure

The following procedure were employed in the course of data gathering: A permit to administer the questionnaire was sought from the office of the Dean of Graduates studies, Sulu state college through a formal letter and then a letter that addressed to the MBHTE, Division-Sulu unit head then, to the Principal of Capual Elementary School to make them aware about the purpose of conducting the study. The launching and administering, as well as the retrieval of the questionnaire were conducted personally by the researcher. The researcher also ensures the confidentially and anonymity of responses to encourage honest answers.

Research Instrument

A survey questionnaire was the main instrument employed to gather data on the extent of reading habits of the selected pupils at Capual Elementary School, MBHTE, division-Sulu during the school year 2023-2024 in the context of preferred places for reading books, Purpose of reading books, Frequency of reading, various print sources preferred for reading

The questionnaire was adapted and patterned from the study of **KUMARA B (2019)**, entitled "Impact of Reading Habits on the Academic achievements: A survey University of Nebraska -Lincoln "

This model encompasses the following domains:

- 1 Preferred places for reading books,
1. Purpose of reading books,
2. Frequency of reading,
3. Various print sources preferred for reading

The research instrument was used in this study consist of two parts. Part I of the questionnaire was focused on obtaining the demographic profile of the pupils in terms of Age, Sex, Grade level, Section.

Part II was focused towards obtaining data on the extent of reading habits of the selected pupils at Capual Elementary School, MBHTE, Sulu in terms of preferred places for reading books, Purpose of reading books, Frequency of reading, various print sources preferred for reading.

Data to be obtained using this questionnaire was analyzed through 5-point modified Likert Scale such as 5=Strongly Agree (SA), 4=Agree (A), 3=Uncertain (U), 2=Disagree (D), 1=Strongly Disagree (SD).

Validity and Reliability

The instrument used in this research was adapted and patterned from the study of Kumar B. entitled "Impact of reading habits to academic achievements"

It is a standardized research instrument with established validity and reliability. However, to suit its usability in the local setting, a slight modification were made and this was subjected to the perusal of at least two (2) experts from the faculty members of the School of Graduate Studies of Sulu state College.

Statistical Treatment of Data

Descriptive and inferential statistical tools was appropriately employed in the treatment of data to be gathered for this study, namely:

- 1) For research problem number one (1), which states: what is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of age, gender, grade level and section, the statistical tools used are frequency counts and percentage to determine the profile of the pupils.
- 2) For research problem number two (2), which states: what is the extent of reading habits to academic learning .The statistical tools used are mean and standard deviation.
- 3) For research problem number three (3), which states: Is there a significant difference in the extent of reading habits of intermediate pupils during the school year 2023-2024. When data are grouped according to age, gender, grade level

and section, the statistical tools used are t-test for independent samples and one-way ANOVA.

4. For research problem number four (4), which states to determine the significant correlation among the sub-categories subsumed under the Reading habits to academic learning of pupils in Kapual Elementary School, MBHTE, division-Sulu? When data are grouped according to age; gender, grade level and section? The statistical tools used are Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (Pearson r)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter presents the analysis, presentation and interpretation of the findings based on the data collected for this study, which aimed to determine the Reading habits to academic learning of selected pupils in Capual elementary school at Omar District, MBHTE, division-Sulu as perceived by the students in school year 2023-2024. It examines the student-respondents' demographic profiles in terms of age, gender, grade level, and section; and the extent of reading habits of intermediate pupils at Capual Elementary School, MBHTE, Sulu in terms of Preferred places for reading books, Purpose of reading books, Frequency of reading, Various print sources preferred for reading, and Impact to academic learning. It also explores the differences and correlations among these variables based on the student-respondents' demographic profiles.

The following are the analysis, presentation, and interpretation of results according to the research questions and the data analysis methods:

1. What is the Socio- demographic Profile of the respondents in terms of 1.1 age, 1.2 gender, 1.3 grade level, and 1.4 section?

1.1 In terms of Age

Table 1.1 presents the demographic profile of the student-respondents at Kapual Elementary School, MBHTE, Sulu in terms of age. The table indicates that out of 100 student-respondents, the majority are between 11-12 years old who make up 42% (42). This is followed by those aged 10 years and below, 13-14 years, and 15 years and above, accounting for 33% (33), 22% (22), AND 3% (3). This shows that the majority of the student-respondents are in their pre-teen stage. This means that there is a difference of at least 9% between the other groups. This implies a slightly skewed age distribution among the student-respondents.

Age	Number of Respondents	Percent
10 years old and below	33	33%
11-12 years old	42	42%

13-14 years old	22	22%
15 years old and above	3	3%
Total	100	100%

Table 1.1 Student-respondents' demographic profile in terms of age.

1.2 In terms of Gender

Table 1.2 presents the demographic profile of the student-respondents at Kapual Elementary School, MBHTE, Sulu in terms of gender. The table indicates that out of 100 student-respondents, it highly concentrated towards females who make up 70% (70). While males account for 30% (30). This means that there is a gender gap of 40% between the female and male groups. This implies a highly skewed gender distribution among the student-respondents.

Table 1.2 Student-respondents' demographic profile in terms of gender.

Gender	Number of Respondents	Percent
Male	30	30%
Female	70	70%
Total	100	100%

1.3 In terms of Grade Level

Table 1.3 presents the demographic profile of the student-respondents at Capual Elementary School, MBHTE, Sulu in terms of grade level. The table indicates that out of 100 student-respondents, the majority are enrolled in grade VI, making up 39% (39). This is followed by grade V and grade IV student-respondents, accounting for 31% (31), and 30% (30) respectively. This shows that majority of the student-respondents are enrolled in grade VI. This means that there is a difference of at least 8% between the other groups. This implies a slightly skewed grade level distribution among the student-respondents.

Grade Level	Number of Respondents	Percent
Grade IV	30	30%
Grade V	31	31%
Grade VI	39	39%
Total	100	100%

Table 1.3 Student-respondents' demographic profile in terms of grade level.

1.4 In terms of Section

Table 1.4 presents the demographic profile of the student-respondents at Kapual Elementary School, MBHTE, Sulu in terms of section. The table indicates that out of 100 student-respondents, it highly concentrated towards section A who make up 94% (94). While section B account for 6% (6). This means that there is a section gap of 88% between the section A and B groups. This implies a highly skewed section distribution among the student-respondents.

Table 1.4 Student-respondents' demographic profile in terms of section.

Section	Number of Respondents	Percent
Section A	94	94%
Section B	6	6%
Total	100	100%

2. What is the extent of reading habits of intermediate pupils at Kapual Elementary School, MBHTE, Sulu in terms of 2.1 Preferred places for reading books, 2.2 Purpose of reading books, 2.3 Frequency of reading, 2.4 Various print sources preferred for reading, and 2.5 Impact to academic learning?

2.1 In the context of Preferred Places for Reading Books

Table 2.1 shows the extent of reading habits of intermediate pupils at Capual Elementary School, MBHTE, Sulu in terms of preferred places for reading books. The result shows that the total mean score is 3.8350, which indicates an overall rating of "Agree". The total standard deviation is 0.88493, which indicates that there is some variation among the student-respondents in their agreement with the statements. This means that the student-respondents have a high positive attitude towards reading habits in the context of preferred places for reading books.

The mean scores indicate that the student-respondents generally agree that they read at home, in the library, and at their friend's home with mean scores of 4.42, 3.97, and 3.60 respectively. However, they moderately agree on reading in the park with a mean score of 3.02. The highest agreement (4.42 mean score) is on the statement "I read only when I am home", suggesting that student-respondents predominantly prefer reading at home. The lowest agree (3.02 mean score) is on the statement "I read in the park", implying that it is not as popular a location for student-respondents' reading activities. The highest mean (4.42) is for reading only when at home, which means that most of the intermediate pupils at Kapual Elementary School prefer to read books at home rather than in other places. The lowest mean (3.02) is for reading in the park, which means that few of the intermediate pupils at Kapual Elementary School like to read books in the park.

Table 2.1 Extent of reading habits of intermediate pupils at Capual Elementary School, MBHTE, Sulu in terms of preferred places in reading books.

Statements	Mean	SD	Rating
1. I read only when I am at home.	4.42	.912	Agree

2. I read in the library.	3.97	1.381	Agree
3. I read in my friend's home.	3.60	1.146	Agree
4. I read in the park.	3.02	1.392	Moderate
Total	3.8350	.88493	Agree

Legend: 4.50-5.00 = Strongly Agree (SA), 3.50-4.49 = Agree (A), 2.50-3.49 = Moderate (M), 1.50-2.49 = Disagree (D), 1.00-1.49 = Strongly Disagree (SD)

2.2 In the context of Purpose of Reading Books

Table 2.2 shows the extent of reading habits of intermediate pupils at Capual Elementary School, MBHTE, Sulu in terms of purpose of reading books. The result shows that the total mean score is 4.33, which indicates an overall rating of "Agree". The total standard deviation is .84154, which indicates that there is some variation among the student-respondents in their agreement with the statements. This means that the student-respondents have a high positive attitude towards reading habits in the context of purpose for reading books.

The mean scores indicate that the student-respondents agree that they read only if they are interested in the topic, that reading is their hobby, read because they want to learn more, read only prior to examinations, read only to prepare notes, read in order to improve their communication skills, and read in order to prepare for next topic. The highest mean score is 4.42 for the statement "I read because I want to learn more," indicating that this is the most agreed upon reason for reading among intermediate pupils at Kapual Elementary School. The lowest mean score is 3.81 for "I read only prior to examinations," suggesting that reading specifically for exam preparation is less common among these students.

Table 2.2 Extent of reading habits of intermediate pupils at Capual Elementary School, MBHTE, Sulu in terms of purpose of reading books.

Statements	Mean	SD	Rating
1. I read only if I am interested in the topic.	4.07	1.233	Agree
2. Reading is my hobby.	4.39	.898	Agree
3. I read because I want to learn more.	4.42	.923	Agree
4. I read only prior to examinations.	3.81	1.228	Agree
5. I read only to prepare notes	3.85	1.234	Agree
6. I read in order to improve my communication skills.	4.13	1.079	Agree
7. I read in order to prepare for next topic.	4.09	1.074	Agree
Total	4.3300	.84154	Agree

Legend: 4.50-5.00 = Strongly Agree (SA), 3.50-4.49 = Agree (A), 2.50-3.49 = Moderate (M), 1.50-2.49 = Disagree (D), 1.00-1.49 = Strongly Disagree (SD)

2.3 In the context of Frequency of Reading

Table 2.3 shows the extent of reading habits of intermediate pupils at Capual Elementary School, MBHTE, Sulu in terms of frequency of reading. The result shows that the total mean score is 3.2, which indicates an overall rating of "Moderate". The total standard deviation is 1.32574, which indicates that there is more variation among the

student-respondents in their agreement with the statements. This means that the student-respondents have a moderate positive attitude towards reading habits in the context of frequency of reading.

The mean scores indicate that the student-respondents agree that they usually spend time reading everyday, read twice/ thrice a week, once in a week, once in a month, or occasionally. The highest mean score is 4.22 for the statement “I usually spend time reading everyday,” indicating that most of the intermediate pupils at Capual Elementary School agree with this statement. The lowest mean score is 2.82 for “I read only once in a month,” falling under the moderate rating. This means that few of the intermediate pupils at Kapual Elementary School agree with this statement.

Table 2.3 Extent of reading habits of intermediate pupils at Kapual Elementary School, MBHTE, Sulu in terms of frequency of reading.

Statements	Mean	SD	Rating
1. I usually spend time reading everyday	4.22	1.151	Agree
2. I read twice/ thrice a week	3.52	1.267	Agree
3. I read only once in a week	2.93	1.38	Moderate
4. I read only once in a month	2.82	1.623	Moderate
5. I read only occasionally	3.08	1.581	Moderate
Total	3.2000	1.32574	Moderate

Legend: 4.50-5.00 = Strongly Agree (SA), 3.50-4.49 = Agree (A), 2.50-3.49 = Moderate (M), 1.50-2.49 = Disagree (D), 1.00-1.49 = Strongly Disagree (SD)

2.4 In the context of Various Print Sources Preferred for Reading

Table 2.4 shows the extent of reading habits of intermediate pupils at Capual Elementary School, MBHTE, Sulu in terms of various print sources preferred for reading. The result shows that the total mean score is 4.095, which indicates an overall rating of “Agree”. The total standard deviation is .90925, which indicates that there is some variation among the student-respondents in their agreement with the statements. This means that the student-respondents have a high positive attitude towards reading habits in the context of various print sources preferred for reading.

The mean scores indicate that the student-respondents agree that they read books/ references, dictionary/encyclopedias, e-books, project reports, novels both Filipino and English, and magazines. The highest mean is 4.18 for “I read books/references,” indicating that this is the most preferred print source among the pupils, as they “Agree” with this statement. The lowest mean is 3.57 for “I read magazines,” which still falls under the “Agree” category but shows that magazines are less preferred compared to other print sources listed.

Table 2.4 Extent of reading habits of intermediate pupils at Capual Elementary School, MBHTE, Sulu in terms of various print sources preferred for reading.

Statements	Mean	SD	Rating
1. I read books/ references.	4.18	1.158	Agree
2. I read dictionary/ encyclopedias.	4.06	1.033	Agree
3. I read e-books.	4.08	1.061	Agree

4. I read project reports.	4.11	1.004	Agree
5. I read novels both Filipino and English.	3.74	1.433	Agree
6. I read magazines.	3.57	1.394	Agree
Total	4.0950	.90925	Agree

Legend: 4.50-5.00 = Strongly Agree (SA), 3.50-4.49 = Agree (A), 2.50-3.49 = Moderate (M), 1.50-2.49 = Disagree (D), 1.00-1.49 = Strongly Disagree (SD)

2.5 In the context of Impact to Academic Learning

Table 2.5 shows the extent of reading habits of intermediate pupils at Capual Elementary School, MBHTE, Sulu in terms of impact to academic learning. The result shows that the total mean score is 4.4150, which indicates an overall rating of “Agree”. The total standard deviation is .67814, which indicates that there is some variation among the student-respondents in their agreement with the statements. This means that the student-respondents have a high positive attitude towards reading habits in the context of impact to academic learning.

The mean scores indicate that the student-respondents agree that they read books/ references, dictionary/encyclopedias, e-books, project reports, novels both Filipino and English, and magazines. The highest mean score (4.44) is associated with the statement “It helps me Improve/sharpen my intellect,” indicating that intermediate pupils at Kapual Elementary School strongly agree that their reading habits significantly enhance their intellectual abilities. The lowest mean score (3.84) is for the statement “It does not help me improve my grades,” suggesting that pupils agree, but to a lesser extent, that reading doesn’t directly impact their academic grades.

Table 2.5 Extent of reading habits of intermediate pupils at Capual Elementary School, MBHTE, Sulu in terms of impact to academic learning.

Statements	Mean	SD	Rating
1. It is a channel for gaining real world of knowledge.	4.37	.991	Agree
2. It effects on my success during the Examination times.	4.28	.996	Agree
3. It enables me to express my feelings.	4.09	1.036	Agree
4. It improves my mental capacity.	4.22	1.021	Agree
5. For me, it is the basic tool of education.	4.42	.878	Agree
6. It enhances my skills in everyday life.	4.42	.867	Agree
7. It helps me Improve/sharpen my intellect.	4.44	.795	Agree
8. Promotes my effective participation in the social life.	4.21	1.028	Agree
9. It does not help me improve my grades.	3.84	1.308	Agree
10. It motivates me to go to school.	4.37	.971	Agree
Total	4.4150	.67814	Agree

Legend: 4.50-5.00 = Strongly Agree (SA), 3.50-4.49 = Agree (A), 2.50-3.49 = Moderate (M), 1.50-2.49 = Disagree (D), 1.00-1.49 = Strongly Disagree (SD)

3. Is there a significant difference on the extent of reading habits of intermediate pupils in Kapual Elementary School, MBHTE, Sulu when data are grouped according to 3.1 age, 3.2 gender, 3.3 grade level, and 3.4 section?

3.1 In terms of Age

Table 3.1 presents the difference on the extent of reading habits of intermediate pupils in Capual Elementary School, MBHTE, Sulu when data are grouped according to age. The variables include Preferred places for reading books, Purpose of reading books, Frequency of reading, Various print sources preferred for reading, and Impact to academic learning. The table shows that the F-values and probability values for all variables are significant at alpha 0.05. Based on the tables, the following interpretation are as follows:

- 1) On the extent of preferred places for reading books, the perceptions of student-respondents aged 13-14 years differ from those aged below 10 years, and 11-12 years, or vice versa.
- 2) On the extent of purpose of reading books, frequency of reading, and various print sources preferred for reading, the perceptions of student-respondents aged below 10 years differ from those aged 11-12 years, or vice versa.
- 3) On the extent of impact to academic learning, the perceptions of student-respondents aged below 10 years differ from those aged 11-12 years, and 13-14 years, or vice versa.

This implies that the student-respondents perceive the extent of reading habits in Capual Elementary School differently depending on their age. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that, “There is no significant difference on the extent of reading habits of intermediate pupils in Capual Elementary School, MBHTE, Sulu when data are grouped according to age.” is rejected.

Table 3.1 Difference on the extent of reading habits of intermediate pupils in Capual Elementary School, MBHTE, Sulu when data are grouped according to age.

Sources of Variation		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Description
Preferred places for reading books	Between Groups	10.582	3	3.527	5.058*	.003	Significant
	Within Groups	66.946	96	.697			
	Total	77.528	99				
Purpose of reading books	Between Groups	8.249	3	2.750	4.267*	.007	Significant
	Within Groups	61.861	96	.644			
	Total	70.110	99				
Frequency of reading	Between Groups	19.872	3	6.624	4.126*	.008	Significant
	Within Groups	154.128	96	1.605			

	Total	174.000	99				
Various print sources preferred for reading	Between Groups	9.728	3	3.243	4.317*	.007	Significant
	Within Groups	72.119	96	.751			
	Total	81.848	99				
Impact to academic learning	Between Groups	10.373	3	3.458	9.443*	.000	Significant
	Within Groups	35.154	96	.366			
	Total	45.528	99				

*Significant at alpha 0.05

A Post Hoc Analysis using Tukey test was conducted to identify which among groups classified according to age have different levels of mean in the extent of Preferred places for reading books, Purpose of reading books, Frequency of reading, Various print sources preferred for reading, and Impact to academic learning when data are grouped according to student-respondents' demographic profile in terms of age.

On Preferred Place for Reading Books: It shows that student-respondents aged 13-14 years obtained the mean difference of $-.7803^*$ with the Standard Error of $.22985$ and p-value of $.005$ over student-respondents aged 10 years and below; and a mean difference of $-.69048^*$ with the Standard Error of $.21978$ and p-value of $.012$ over student-respondents aged 11-12 years which are all significant at alpha 0.05.

On Purpose of Reading Books: It shows that student-respondents aged 10 years and below obtained the mean difference of $.65584^*$ with the Standard Error of $.18673$ and p-value of $.004$ over student-respondents aged 11-12 years which is significant at alpha 0.05.

On Frequency of Reading: It shows that student-respondents aged 10 years and below obtained the mean difference of -1.02381^* with the Standard Error of $.29475$ and p-value of $.004$ over student-respondents aged 11-12 years which is significant at alpha 0.05.

On Various Print Sources Preferred for Reading: It shows that student-respondents aged 10 years and below obtained the mean difference of $.70887^*$ with the Standard Error of $.20162$ and p-value of $.004$ over student-respondents aged 11-12 years which is significant at alpha 0.05.

On Impact to Academic Learning: It shows that student-respondents aged 10 years and below obtained the mean difference of $.72078^*$ with the Standard Error of $.14077$ and p-value of $.000$ over student-respondents aged 11-12 years; and a mean difference of $.61364^*$ with the Standard Error of $.16656$ and p-value of $.002$ over student-respondents aged 13-14 years which are all significant at alpha 0.05.

Table 3.1.1 Multiple comparison of the extent of reading habits of intermediate pupils in Kapual Elementary School, MBHTE, Sulu by age.

*The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level

Dependent Variable	(I) Grouping by Age	(J) Grouping Age	Mean Difference (I - J)	Std. Error	Sig.
Preferred places for reading books	13-14 years old	10 years old and below	-.78030*	.22985	.005
		11-12 years old	-.69048*	.21978	.012
		15 years old and above	-1.25000	.51395	.078
Purpose of reading books	10 years old and below	11-12 years old	.65584*	.18673	.004
		13-14 years old	.50000	.22095	.114
		15 years old and above	.39394	.48407	.848
Frequency of reading	10 years old and below	11-12 years old	-1.02381*	.29475	.004
		13-14 years old	-.42424	.34875	.618
		15 years old and above	-.33333	.76408	.972
Various print sources preferred for reading	10 years old and below	11-12 years old	.70887*	.20162	.004
		13-14 years old	.55303	.23856	.101
		15 years old and above	.53030	.52266	.741
Impact academic learning to	10 years old and below	11-12 years old	.72078*	.14077	.000
		13-14 years old	.61364*	.16656	.002
		15 years old and above	.36364	.36491	.752

3.2 In terms of Gender

Table 3.2 presents the difference on the extent of reading habits of intermediate pupils in Kapual Elementary School, MBHTE, Sulu when data are grouped according to gender. The variables include Preferred places for reading books, Purpose of reading books, Frequency of reading, Various print sources preferred for reading, and Impact to academic learning. The table shows that the mean difference and probability values for all variables, except for preferred places for reading books aspect, are not significant at alpha 0.05. This means that the extent of these variables does not affect the perceptions of male and female student-respondents differently. However, on the extent of preferred

places for reading books aspect, male student-respondents perceive differently from those females. This implies that the student-respondents perceive the extent of reading habits at Kapual Elementary School in the same way regardless of their gender, except for preferred places for reading books aspect. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that, “There is no significant difference on the extent of reading habits of intermediate pupils in Kapual Elementary School, MBHTE, Sulu when data are grouped according to gender.” is accepted.

Table 3.2 Difference on the extent of reading habits of intermediate pupils in Capual Elementary School, MBHTE, Sulu when data are grouped according to gender.

Variables	Grouping	Mean	SD	Mean Difference	t	Sig.	Description
Preferred places for reading books	Male	4.1167	.87773	.40238	2.12*	0.037	Significant
	Female	3.7143	.86632				
Purpose of reading books	Male	4.3000	.74971	-.04286	-0.232	.817	Not Significant
	Female	4.3429	.88278				
Frequency of reading	Male	3.4333	1.16511	.33333	1.154	.251	Not Significant
	Female	3.1000	1.38470				
Various print sources preferred for reading	Male	3.8333	1.00287	-.37381	-1.90	0.059	Not Significant
	Female	4.2071	.84910				
Impact to academic learning	Male	4.2667	.62606	-.21190	-1.440	.153	Not Significant
	Female	4.4786	.69384				

*Significant at alpha 0.05

3.3 In terms of Grade Level

Table 3.3 presents the difference on the extent of reading habits of intermediate pupils in Kapual Elementary School, MBHTE, Sulu when data are grouped according to grade level. The variables include Preferred places for reading books, Purpose of reading books, Frequency of reading, Various print sources preferred for reading, and Impact to academic learning. The table shows that the F-values and probability values for all variables are significant at alpha 0.05. Based on the tables, the following interpretation are as follows:

- 1) On the extent of preferred places for reading books, the perceptions of grade VI student-respondents differ from those grade IV, and V student-respondents, or vice versa.
- 2) On the extent frequency of reading, the perceptions of grade V student-respondents differ from those grade IV, and VI student-respondents, or vice versa.
- 3) On the extent of purpose of reading books, various print sources preferred for reading, and impact to academic learning, the perceptions of grade IV student-

respondents differ from those grade V and VI student-respondents, or vice versa.

This implies that the student-respondents perceive the extent of reading habits in Capual Elementary School differently depending on their grade level. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that, “There is no significant difference on the extent of reading habits of intermediate pupils in Kapual Elementary School, MBHTE, Sulu when data are grouped according to grade level.” is rejected.

Table 3.3 Difference on the extent of reading habits of intermediate pupils in Capual Elementary School, MBHTE, Sulu when data are grouped according to grade level.

Sources of Variation		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Description
Preferred places for reading books	Between Groups	13.775	2	6.887	10.479	.000	Significant
	Within Groups	63.753	97	.657			
	Total	77.528	99				
Purpose of reading books	Between Groups	9.523	2	4.762	7.624	.001	Significant
	Within Groups	60.587	97	.625			
	Total	70.110	99				
Frequency of reading	Between Groups	32.736	2	16.368	11.239	.000	Significant
	Within Groups	141.264	97	1.456			
	Total	174.000	99				
Various print sources preferred for reading	Between Groups	27.761	2	13.881	24.894	.000	Significant
	Within Groups	54.086	97	.558			
	Total	81.848	99				
Impact to academic learning	Between Groups	13.097	2	6.548	19.586	.000	Significant
	Within Groups	32.431	97	.334			
	Total	45.528	99				

*Significant at alpha 0.05

A Post Hoc Analysis using Tukey test was conducted to identify which among groups classified according to grade level have different levels of mean in the extent of Preferred places for reading books, Purpose of reading books, Frequency of reading, Various print sources preferred for reading, and Impact to academic learning when data are grouped according to student-respondents’ demographic profile in terms of grade level.

On Preferred Place for Reading Books: It shows that grade VI student-respondents obtained the mean difference of $-.72821^*$ with the Standard Error of $.19688$ and p-value of $.001$ over grade IV student-respondents; and a mean difference of $-.7895^*$ with the Standard Error of $.19507$ and p-value of $.000$ over grade V student-respondents which are all significant at alpha 0.05.

On Purpose of Reading Books: It shows that grade IV student-respondents obtained the mean difference of $.70323^*$ with the Standard Error of $.20241$ and p-value of $.002$ over grade V student-respondents; and a mean difference of $.64615^*$ with the

Standard Error of .19193 and p-value of .003 over grade VI student-respondents which are all significant at alpha 0.05.

On Frequency of Reading: It shows that grade V student-respondents obtained the mean difference of 1.43333* with the Standard Error of .30907 and p-value of .000 over grade IV student-respondents; and a mean difference of .94872* with the Standard Error of .29038 and p-value of .004 over grade VI student-respondents which are all significant at alpha 0.05.

On Various Print Sources Preferred for Reading: It shows that grade IV student-respondents obtained the mean difference of .83387* with the Standard Error of .19124 and p-value of .000 over grade V student-respondents; and a mean difference of 1.27308* with the Standard Error of .18134 and p-value of .000 over grade VI student-respondents which are all significant at alpha 0.05.

On Impact to Academic Learning: It shows that grade IV student-respondents obtained the mean difference of .75699* with the Standard Error of .14809 and p-value of .000 over grade V student-respondents; and a mean difference of .81282* with the Standard Error of .14042 and p-value of .000 over grade VI student-respondents which are all significant at alpha 0.05.

Table 3.3.1 Multiple comparison of the extent of reading habits of intermediate pupils in Kapual Elementary School, MBHTE, Sulu by grade level.

Dependent Variable	(I) Grouping by Age	(J) Grouping Age	Mean Difference (I - J)	Std. Error	Sig.
Preferred places for reading books	Grade VI	Grade IV	-0.72821*	0.19688	0.001
		Grade V	-0.7895*	0.19507	.000
Purpose of reading books	Grade IV	Grade V	0.70323*	0.20241	0.002
		Grade VI	0.64615*	0.19193	0.003
Frequency of reading	Grade V	Grade IV	1.43333*	0.30907	.000
		Grade VI	0.94872*	0.29038	0.004
Various print sources preferred for reading	Grade IV	Grade V	.83387*	.19124	.000
		Grade VI	1.27308*	.18134	.000
Impact to academic learning	Grade IV	Grade V	0.75699*	0.14809	.000
		Grade VI	0.81282*	0.14042	.000

*The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level

3.4 In terms of Section

Table 3.4 presents the difference on the extent of reading habits of intermediate pupils in Kapual Elementary School, MBHTE, Sulu when data are grouped according to section. The variables include Preferred places for reading books, Purpose of reading books, Frequency of reading, Various print sources preferred for reading, and Impact to academic learning. The table shows that the mean difference and probability values for all variables are not significant at alpha 0.05. This means that the extent of these variables does not affect the perceptions of student-respondents from section A and B differently. This implies that the student-respondents perceive the extent of reading habits at Kapual Elementary School in the same way regardless of their section. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that, "There is no significant difference on the extent of reading habits of intermediate pupils in Kapual Elementary School, MBHTE, Sulu when data are grouped according to section." is accepted.

Table 3.4 Difference on the extent of reading habits of intermediate pupils in Capual Elementary School, MBHTE, Sulu when data are grouped according to section.

Variables	Grouping	Mean	SD	Mean Difference	t	Sig.	Description
Preferred places for reading books	Male	3.8191	.89758	-.26418	-0.707	0.481	Not Significant
	Female	4.0833	.66458				
Purpose of reading books	Male	4.3298	.84737	-.00355	-0.01	0.992	Not Significant
	Female	4.3333	.81650				
Frequency of reading	Male	3.1702	1.32501	-.49645	-.888	0.377	Not Significant
	Female	3.6667	1.36626				
Various print sources preferred for reading	Male	4.1223	.90306	.45567	1.193	.236	Not Significant
	Female	3.6667	.98319				
Impact to academic learning	Male	4.4362	.67694	0.35284	1.239	0.218	Not Significant
	Female	4.0833	.66458				

*Significant at alpha 0.05

4. Is there a significant correlation among the sub-categories subsumed under the reading habits among intermediate pupils in Kapual Elementary School, MBHTE, division-Sulu?

Table 4 presents the correlation among the sub-categories subsumed under the reading habits among intermediate pupils in Kapual Elementary School, MBHTE, division-Sulu. The table shows that the computed Pearson correlation Coefficients (Pearson r) between these variables, except for Purpose of reading books and Frequency of reading, Frequency of reading and Various print sources preferred for reading, are significant at alpha 0.05. Specifically, the degree of correlations among the sub-categories subsumed under the reading habits among intermediate pupils in Kapual Elementary School, MBHTE, division-Sulu are:

- 1) Moderate positive correlations between preferred places for reading books and purpose of reading books, and various print sources preferred for reading, or vice versa; low positive correlations between preferred places for reading books and frequency of reading, and impact to academic learning, or vice versa.
- 2) No correlations between purpose of reading books and frequency of reading; moderate positive correlations between purpose of reading books and various print sources preferred for reading, or vice versa; high positive correlations between purpose of reading books and impact to academic learning, or vice versa.
- 3) No correlations between frequency of reading and various print sources preferred for reading; low negative correlations between frequency of reading and impact to academic learning, or vice versa.
- 4) Moderate positive correlations between various print sources preferred for reading and impact to academic learning, or vice versa.

This means that as one variable increases, the other variable also tends to increase or decrease, and that these relationships are not likely to be random. The strongest correlation is between purpose of reading books and impact to academic learning, or vice versa ($r = 0.528$, $p < 0.01$), which implies that student-respondents who have high purpose of reading books also experience high impact from reading books for their academic learning. The weakest correlation is between frequency of reading and impact to academic learning, or vice versa ($r = -.200$, $p < 0.01$), which implies that student-respondents who read books less frequently also experience high impact from reading books for their academic learning. The other correlations are not significant which means that there is no linear relationship between the variables. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that, "There is no significant correlation among the sub-categories subsumed under the reading habits among intermediate pupils in Kapual Elementary School, MBHTE, division of Sulu." is rejected.

Table 4 Correlation among the sub-categories subsumed under the reading habits among intermediate pupils in Capual Elementary School, MBHTE, division-Sulu.

Variables		Pearson <i>r</i>	Sig.	N	Description
Dependent	Independent				
Preferred places for reading books	Purpose of reading books	.338*	.001	100	Moderate
	Frequency of reading	.265*	.008	100	Low
	Various print sources preferred for reading	.246*	.014	100	Moderate
	Impact to academic learning	.225*	.025	100	Low

Purpose of reading books	Frequency of reading	-.005	.957	100	
	Various print sources preferred for reading	.473*	.000	100	Moderate
	Impact to academic learning	.528*	.000	100	High
Frequency of reading	Various print sources preferred for reading	.001	.993	100	
	Impact to academic learning	-.200*	.046	100	Low
Various print sources preferred for reading	Impact to academic learning	.419*	.000	100	Moderate

*Correlation coefficient is significant at alpha .05

Correlation Coefficient Scales Adopted from Hopkins, Will (2002):

0.0-0.1 = Nearly Zero; 0.1-0.3 = Low; 0.3-0.5 = Moderate; 0.5-0.7 = High; 0.7-0.9 = Very High; 0.9-1 = Nearly Perfect

Conclusions

The study concludes that:

- 1) The skewed distributions of student-respondents' age, gender, grade level, and section may affect the validity and reliability of the research findings.
- 2) The student-respondents generally have a positive attitude towards reading habits, which may imply that they enjoy reading for their academic learning. However, the moderate attitude towards frequency of reading may suggest that they do not read as often as they should.

Reading habits are well-planned and deliberate patterns of study which has attained a form of consisting on the part of the students towards understanding academic subjects and passing at examination (e-journal, 2022).

Source: The Effects Of Reading Habit Towards Student Reading at <https://e-journal.stkipsiliwangi.ac.id>, 2022

- 3) The extent of perceptions of reading habits of intermediate pupils in Kapual Elementary School, MBHTE, Sulu varies depending on their age and grade level, but not on their gender and section. This may imply that the reading habits of the student-respondents are influenced by their developmental and academic stages, but not by their biological and social factors.

The study was anchored on the principles of Lou Vygotsky's zone of proximal development (1978). It can be related to this study because of the factor that the environment of the child may influence their reading habits.

- 4) The reading habits of the student-respondents are related to each other in different ways, and that some sub-categories have more influence on their academic learning than others. This may imply that the student-respondents have different

motivations and preferences for reading, and that reading more frequently does not necessarily lead to better academic outcomes.

Recommendations

This study recommends the following:

- 1) The principal of Kapual Elementary School may implement a school-wide reading program that encourages and rewards students for reading more books of different genres and levels.
- 2) Teachers from Kapual Elementary School may use various strategies to motivate and engage their students in reading, by creating a positive reading environment.
- 3) Parents may foster a love of reading in their children by reading with them and to them every day, exposing them to a variety of books and reading materials, and praising their efforts and achievements.
- 4) Students may develop good reading habits by reading more often and more widely, choosing books that interest and challenge them and setting and achieving their own reading goals.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Prior to data collection, participants were provided with detailed information about the study's purpose, procedures, and confidentiality measures. Informed consent was obtained from all participants before their involvement in the research.

Participants' identities and sensitive information were kept confidential throughout the study. Data were securely stored and only accessed by the research ethics committee for analysis purposes.

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